

ESTABLISHING EFFECTIVE AND LEGALLY CERTAIN REGIONAL LEGISLATION

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Abstract

The conflicting norms in the division of authority between the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (Kemenkumham) and the Ministry of Home Affairs (Kemendagri) in the process of harmonization and facilitation of Draft Regional Regulations (Raperda) not only give rise to administrative problems, but also give rise to various implications that can hinder the effectiveness of the law in the formation of regional regulations. This research aims to answer questions regarding the nature of the formation of effective and legally certain regional legal products, the stages of the formation of effective and legally certain regional legal products, and the ideal concept of the process of forming effective and legally certain regional legal products. This research is a normative legal research using the statutory approach, conceptual approach, case approach, and comparative approach. The results of the study indicate that the essence of regional regulations is as a tool to regulate and adjust regional policies according to the needs of local communities, within the limits of authority established by national law. The formation of regional legal products often faces a conflict between formal legal certainty and the effectiveness of implementation that suits regional conditions. The formation of regional legal products must be based on responsible autonomy with limited central oversight, so that the resulting law is participatory, responsive, and maintains the unity of the national system. The recommendation is that the formation of regional regulations must go through systematic and careful stages to ensure their effectiveness and legal certainty. This includes planning, drafting academic papers, discussions, ratification, socialization, implementation, and monitoring and enforcement, all in accordance with higher-level regulations. To ensure regional legal products are effective and legally certain, the formulation paradigm must shift from a normative focus to a contextual, collaborative, and dialogical approach to more responsive regional autonomy.

Keywords: Reconstruction, Regional Legal Products, Effective.

INTRODUCTION

In the approach to achieving the goals of the Indonesian state as a state of law, (Sidharta, 2017) philosophically, it has the responsibility to ensure that the process of making laws (construction), improvements (reconstruction) must reflect the principles of justice and legal certainty, as mandated in Article 1 Paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which states that, "The State of Indonesia is a state of law". This provision emphasizes that all state actions, including the formation of regional regulations (hereinafter referred to as Perda) must be based on law and uphold the principles of justice and legal certainty. (Rosmini, 2017)

Justice in the formation of Regional Regulations requires that the laws formed must be able to accommodate the interests of the community fairly, ensure that community rights are respected and clearly regulated, and provide solutions to problems that exist in the region. Meanwhile, the principle of legal certainty demands that the resulting laws can be clearly

understood and applied consistently, providing a sense of security and order. The affirmation of this principle is in line with the contents of Article 28D Paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution, which states that: "Everyone has the right to recognition, guarantees, protection, and certainty of fair law as well as equal treatment before the law." In light of the aforementioned philosophical foundation, theoretically, the creation of regional legal products (Regional Regulations) must reflect a balance between procedural transparency and the fulfillment of community needs as key elements in regional legislative discourse. (Riskiyono, 2015) Transparency in the process of creating Regional Regulations ensures accountability and openness, while attention to community needs ensures that the resulting regulations align with the public interest, especially in today's era of implementing good governance principles. (Suhardono, 2001)

In its implementation, the drafting of regional regulations involves various relevant stakeholders to ensure fair representation for all levels of society. However, this process must be carried out carefully to avoid being trapped by sectoral interests that could hinder the effectiveness and productivity of the regulations. Therefore, to achieve a balance between transparent procedures and orientation to community needs as the main principles in every stage of regional regulation formation, a harmonized approach and consultation, evaluation, facilitation, verification, and clarification in the discourse by authorized institutions are required.

In addition to the authority for consultation, evaluation, facilitation, verification, and clarification, which rests with the Ministry of Home Affairs, the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (Kemenkumham) currently exercises the authority to harmonize draft regional regulations, as stipulated in Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number 22 of 2018 concerning the Harmonization of Draft Legislation Formed in the Regions by Legislative Drafters.

The Ministry of Law and Human Rights' harmonization process for draft regional regulations from regional governments and the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) must be completed within a maximum of 10 working days. This is in accordance with the provisions stipulated in Circular Letter of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number M.HH-01.PP.04.02 of 2022 concerning the Methods and Procedures for Harmonizing, Unifying, and Consolidating the Concept of Draft Regional Head Regulations.

Furthermore, regarding the timeframe, both the harmonization process carried out by the Ministry of Law and Human Rights and the facilitation process carried out by the Ministry of Home Affairs (Director General of Regional Autonomy) require 25 days. In practice, this timeframe has not been implemented as intended, with frequent cases where the harmonization and facilitation processes cannot be completed within the specified timeframe. These delays have had a serious impact on the legislative process at the regional level. The conflicting norms in the division of authority between the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (Kemenkumham) and the Ministry of Home Affairs (Kemendagri) in the process of harmonization and facilitation of Draft Regional Regulations (Raperda) not only give rise to

administrative problems, but also give rise to various philosophical, theoretical, juridical, and sociological implications that can hinder the effectiveness of law in the formation of regional regulations.

Thus, the conflicting norms regarding the division of authority between the Ministry of Law and Human Rights and the Ministry of Home Affairs are not merely technical issues but also have broad implications for the national legal system. If not immediately addressed through clear and effective legal policies, this conflict has the potential to undermine the principles of justice, legal certainty, and the effectiveness of regulations within the government system, both at the central and regional levels. Concrete steps are needed to establish clear boundaries of authority so that the harmonization and facilitation of the Draft Regional Regulation can run optimally and in line with the principles of the rule of law. Therefore, this study will examine the nature of the formation of effective and legally certain regional legal products, the stages of the formation of effective and legally certain regional legal products, and the ideal concept of the process of forming effective and legally certain regional legal products.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used by the researcher is normative research or also called doctrinal research. (Soemitro, 1983) Normative legal research is also called dogmatic legal research which studies, maintains and develops positive legal structures with logical structures. (Muhaimin, 2020) In order to answer the problems in this study, the approaches used include the Philosophical Approach, the Legislative Approach, the Conceptual Approach, the Case Approach and the Comparative Approach. The types and sources of legal materials are in the form of Primary Legal Materials, Secondary Legal Materials and Tertiary Legal Materials. The technique of collecting legal materials in this study was obtained through Library Research. The legal materials collected and obtained in the study were analyzed through legal interpretation and then processed deductively, namely drawing conclusions from a general problem to the specific problem faced, then the analysis was carried out using qualitative methods. The collected legal materials were processed through inventory, classification, and systematization. They were then grouped and analyzed in stages according to the problem groups that were the focus of the research.

DISCUSSION

1. The Essence of the Formation of Effective and Legally Certain Regional Legal Products

The primary actors in social and state life are legal subjects, namely humans. These humans, on the one hand, can create or shape laws, but on the other hand, are also subject to the legal norms they create themselves. (Subhan, 2015) The transformation of the governance paradigm, marked by the decentralization of authority, has positioned regional governments as the primary axis in realizing equitable collective prosperity. Within this framework, the role of regional governments in implementing laws and regulations is highly strategic, particularly in the formation of regional regulations that must remain in line with the

principle of the hierarchy of legal norms. Regional regulations, as an emanation of national law, are not merely normative instruments governing social life but also concrete manifestations of the principle of substantive justice rooted in the legal system.

Within the framework of regional autonomy, regional legislative authority, based on the principle of representation, ensures that every regulation created is not only based on formal procedures but also reflects the aspirations of the community. This principle emphasizes that the formation of regional laws must address real needs at the local level while remaining within the framework of the national legal system. From a constitutional law perspective, regional regulations represent a concrete form of legislative function at the regional level, possessing unique characteristics compared to other legal products.

In line with this, Jimly Asshiddiqie categorizes legal products in Indonesia into three main forms, one of which is regulatory decisions (*regeling*). In the context of regional government, Perda is included in the *regeling* category which functions as implementing regulations for laws at the regional level. (Asshiddiqie, 2006) Thus, the existence of Perda is not only a manifestation of regional legislative authority, but also a normative instrument that must meet the principles of effectiveness and legal certainty.

Based on the description above, in the context of the essence of the formation of effective and legally certain regional legal products, including the formation of Regional Regulations as regional legal products, it becomes an important instrument in implementing the principles of decentralization and regional autonomy, as mandated by the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and other laws and regulations. Thus, in essence, Regional Regulations are not just legal regulations made by regional governments, but also a tool to regulate, manage, and adjust regional policies according to the needs and characteristics of local communities, within the limits of authority determined by national law.

To be able to confirm the essence of the formation of effective regional legal products and legal certainty as constructed above, the formation of regional legal products, especially Regional Regulations (Perda), must follow systematic stages to have effectiveness and legal certainty. Each stage must be carried out carefully to ensure that the resulting regulations can be implemented properly and do not conflict with higher laws and regulations, such as the planning stage; preparation of academic papers and draft regional regulations; discussion and legislation; Ratification and Evaluation by the Central/Provincial Government; socialization and implementation; monitoring, evaluation, and law enforcement. By following these stages, the formation of regional legal products can fulfill the principles of effectiveness and legal certainty, so that Regional Regulations can function as regulatory instruments that are adaptive to community needs and in line with the national legal system.

2. Stages of Establishing Effective and Legally Certain Regional Legal Products

Article 39 of Law Number 12 of 2011 stipulates that planning for the preparation of Regency/City Regional Regulations is carried out in the Regency/City Prolegda. The planning stage is the first step taken to achieve the goal of establishing good Legislation.

One of the planning activities for the formation of legislation is the preparation of an academic paper. Through the study and preparation of an academic paper, it is hoped that the legislation created will meet the objectives of its formation and can be implemented and enforced. The academic paper provides an explanation or explanation of why the regulation was created. Law Number 12 of 2011 concerning the Formation of Legislation requires an academic paper in the process of forming legislation.

The legal basis for the formation of the Academic Manuscript is Article 57 of Law Number 12 of 2011 which stipulates that: (1) The preparation of the Academic Manuscript for the Draft Provincial Regulation is carried out in accordance with the techniques for preparing the Academic Manuscript. (2) Provisions regarding the techniques for preparing the Academic Manuscript as referred to in paragraph (1) are listed in Attachment I which is an integral part of this Law.

As based on Article 63 of Law Number 12 of 2011, the provisions regarding the preparation of Provincial Regional Regulations as referred to in Articles 56 to 62 apply *mutatis mutandis* to the preparation of Regency/City Regional Regulations.

In comparison, Law No. 10/2004 does not require the provision of an Academic Paper as part of the legislative drafting process. Therefore, given the urgency of the Academic Paper in the drafting of legislation, there has been a significant setback in the inclusion of the Academic Paper.

Previously, in the Decree of the Head of the National Legal Development Agency Number: G-159.Pr.09.10 of 1994 concerning Technical Instructions for the Preparation of Academic Manuscripts of Legislation, it was emphasized that the Academic Manuscript is an inseparable part of the preparation of a draft legislation because it contains regulatory ideas and the content of the legislation in certain fields that have been reviewed systematically, holistically and futuristically from various scientific aspects. With the affirmation of the Academic Manuscript as an inseparable part of the preparation of draft legislation.

Mechanism for the formation of Regional Regulations Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 120 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 80 of 2015 concerning the Formation of Regional Legal Products:

No.	Stages	Description	Legal basis
1	Planning for the Formation of Regional Legal Products	The preparation of the Provincial Regional Regulation Formation Program (Propemperda) is carried out by the DPRD and the Governor to determine the priority scale of the draft Provincial Regional Regulation (Perda).	Article 15
2	Determination of Regional Regulation Proposal	The drafted regional regulation was agreed upon and determined in a plenary meeting of the Provincial DPRD.	Article 16
3	Drafting of Regional Regulations	The draft Provincial Regulation is prepared based on the Propemperda, may involve a special committee, and is continued by Bapemperda if the special committee is not completed within 1 year.	Article 33
4	Academic Manuscript	The Provincial Legal Bureau harmonizes the Academic	Article 23

	Alignment	Draft of the Provincial Regulation with Regional Apparatus and other stakeholders.	
5	Drafting of Regional Regulation	The Draft Regional Head Regulation (Perkada) is prepared by the Regional Head based on the authority or orders of higher legislation.	Articles 25-31
6	Drafting of District/City Regional Regulations	The procedure for drafting regional regulations in districts/cities follows the same principles as in provinces with local adjustments.	Article 32
7	Submission of Draft Regional Regulation	Draft Regional Regulations can be submitted by DPRD members, commissions, joint commissions, or Bapemperda based on the established Propemperda.	Article 33
8	Drafting of Regional Regulation Proposals Outside of Schedule	In an emergency or urgent need, the DPRD or Governor can submit a draft Regional Regulation outside the schedule set out in the Propemperda.	Article 16
9	Evaluation and Supervision	Supervision is carried out to ensure that regional legal products comply with higher legal provisions and meet the needs of the community.	Article 34
10	Discussion of the Draft Governor's Regulation	The team discussed the draft gubernatorial regulation.	Article 79
11	Coordination Initial by Team	After the discussion was completed, each page of the draft gubernatorial regulation received a coordination initial from the team.	Article 80 paragraph (1)
12	Submission to the Governor	The team leader submits the draft gubernatorial regulation that has been initialed for coordination to the governor through the regional secretary.	Article 80 paragraph (2)
14	Changes and Improvements by the Regional Secretary	The regional secretary can make changes or improvements to the draft that has been initialed for coordination, which is then returned to the head of the initiating Regional Apparatus.	Article 81 paragraph (1)
15	Coordination Initial by Team for Improvement	The draft revision must be re-initialed by the coordination team after changes have been made by the regional secretary.	Article 81 paragraph (3)
16	Submission of Improvements to the Governor	The regional secretary submits a draft regulation that has been refined with coordination initials to the governor for stipulation.	Article 81 paragraph (3)
17	Facilitation of Draft Regional Regulations and Regional Head Regulations	Facilitation is carried out after the first-level discussions are completed. Facilitation is not implemented if the draft Regional Regulation or Regional Head Regulation has been evaluated.	Article 88A
18	Signing of Facilitation Results	The results of the facilitation are signed by the regional secretary on behalf of the governor (for provinces) or regent/mayor (for districts/cities) and submitted to the relevant parties.	Article 88B
19	Noreg Application Submission	The governor or regent/mayor submits a Noreg application to the Minister or governor via a letter signed by the regional secretary.	Article 101
20	Noreg Verification	The Minister or governor verifies the revised draft Regional Regulation. If it does not comply with the results of the Evaluation and Facilitation, the Noreg will not be issued.	Article 101 paragraph (5)

21	Noreg Determination	Draft Regional Regulations that have received Noreg can be stipulated by the regional head and promulgated in the regional gazette.	Article 103 paragraph (1)
22	Noreg Reporting	The Governor as the representative of the central government is obliged to report Regional Regulations that have received Noreg to the Minister through the Legal Bureau of the Secretariat General.	Article 103 paragraph (2)
23	Noreg Grant	The issuance of Noreg is carried out by the Head of the Legal Bureau of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Home Affairs (for Provincial Regulations) or the provincial legal bureau (for Regency/City Regulations).	Article 104
24	Submission of Noreg Application	Applications for granting Noreg for draft Provincial and Regency/City Regulations are submitted either directly or indirectly to the Legal Bureau of the Secretariat General.	Article 106

From the perspective of legal effectiveness theory, the stages of Regional Regulation (Perda) formation described above can be analyzed in terms of how the process effectively supports the achievement of legal objectives. Legal effectiveness theory assesses the extent to which laws are effectively implemented and influence public behavior.

In this context, the existing stages demonstrate that a structured system of planning, drafting, and oversight can create a clear and measurable legal basis. The process, which involves various parties (the Regional People's Representative Council, the Governor, regional officials, and the community), increases the likelihood of realizing regulations that are relevant and aligned with regional needs.

3. The Ideal Concept of the Process of Forming Regional Legal Products that are Effective and Have Legal Certainty

From the perspective of the theory of legal certainty, the system for forming national legislation requires a clear, non-overlapping institutional structure and firm authority in every stage of regulatory formation, including harmonization and evaluation.

Legal certainty can only be achieved if there is a rigid division of institutional duties that can be accounted for normatively and institutionally. In this context, the establishment of a single institution as a central authority to manage the entire process of formulating legislation, as recommended by the OECD, does offer advantages in terms of consolidation of authority and efficiency of cross-sectoral coordination. However, in the practice of Indonesian governance, which adheres to the principle of regional autonomy, this centralized approach can give rise to serious contradictions with the principle of decentralization as stipulated in Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

Consequently, a clear separation of authority is necessary based on hierarchy and type of regulation. To ensure consistency between national and local regulations, the authority to harmonize and evaluate draft regional regulations (Ranperda) should be designated exclusively as a structural function inherent in the Ministry of Home Affairs. This authority is not merely administrative, but rather substantive, serving as a form of oversight of regional legal norms to ensure they align with the principles of statutory regulation formation and do

not conflict with the national interest.

Institutionally, it is ideal to establish a Directorate for Harmonization and Facilitation of Regional Legal Products, which is structurally under the Directorate General of Regional Autonomy of the Ministry of Home Affairs. This Directorate is tasked with: (1) conducting reviews and harmonizing the substance of Draft Regional Regulations against higher-level laws and regulations; (2) providing legal and administrative recommendations on Draft Regional Regulations before they are stipulated by the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) and regional heads; and (3) conducting periodic evaluations of existing regional regulations, in order to identify potential disharmony and overlap between regulations in the regions.

Thus, the process of harmonizing regional regulations falls entirely within the purview of the Ministry of Home Affairs' concurrent autonomy, and is not interfered with by the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, whose authority focuses on harmonizing central regulations such as laws, government regulations, and presidential regulations. This step also aligns with the principle of subsidiarity in regional autonomy theory, which states that matters that can be effectively resolved by regional governments need not be delegated to the central government, in this case, to ministries unrelated to the administration of regional government.

Giving the Ministry of Home Affairs full authority in harmonizing and evaluating regional regulations actually strengthens substantive regional autonomy, without sacrificing national legal certainty, as long as the principles of hierarchy and regulatory synchronization are maintained through measurable and accountable technocratic mechanisms. The characteristics of government authority include: expressly implied, clearly stated in terms of intent and purpose, time-bound, and subject to written legal limitations. The authority can be abstract (general), such as creating regulations, or concrete (definite), in the form of a decree, decision, or plan, such as creating spatial planning and providing advice. (Santoso, 2019)

The authority vested in the President is obtained through Article 4 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia as the holder of governmental power, including in forming the Cabinet. Thus, the power of the Cabinet is actually the implementation of the President's power which is handed over to the Ministers, so that the Ministers are responsible to the President.

The relationship between the President and the Ministers arose from the Constitutional convention which gives the President the power to appoint Ministers in forming the Cabinet, and now the formation of the Cabinet is regulated by law. (Asshiddiqie, 2006) The existence of the Cabinet or Ministers formed by the President is essentially formed in order to implement the power of the Presidential Government. The formation of the Cabinet is intended to implement the power of the Government and the people who hold the position of Minister will carry out Government affairs based on expertise, intelligence in their fields, and so on. Ministers as constitutional organs of the presidential system are tasked with assisting the President in carrying out government duties. In order to implement these duties and authorities, ministers can create Ministerial Regulations. (Asshiddiqie, 2005)

Ministerial Regulations and Ministerial Instructions at this time were normatively emphasized as only being formed based on and derived from higher-level legislation. Thus, the formation of Ministerial Regulations was limited to only receiving delegation from higher-level regulations and could not be formed based on authority. Such Ministerial Regulations, when linked to Maria Farida Indrati's opinion at the time, were categorized as policy regulations whose validity was recognized but only internally regulated. (Soeprapto, 2007)

Based on the provisions of Article 58 paragraph (2) of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 13 of 2022 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 12 of 2011 concerning the Formation of Legislation, the authority in question is given to the ministry that organizes government affairs in the legal sector. Thus, in order for the Ministry of Home Affairs to obtain the basis of authority in carrying out these duties, the related provisions need to be reconstructed as in the table below.

Chapter	Pre-Reconstruction	Post Reconstruction
Article 58 Paragraph (2)	Harmonization, consolidation and strengthening of the concept of the Draft Provincial Regional Regulation as referred to in paragraph (1) is carried out by the vertical agency of the ministry or institution that carries out government affairs in the field of Formation of Legislation.	The harmonization, consolidation, and strengthening of the concept of the Draft Provincial Regulation and the Draft Regulation of the Head of Region is carried out by the Ministry of Home Affairs as part of its authority in fostering and supervising the implementation of regional government.

Next, in relation to the scope of facilitation, several reconstructions of the provisions are required which can be included in the following table:

Name of Regulation	Chapter	Pre-Reconstruction	Post Reconstruction
Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 120 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 80 of 2015 concerning the Formation of Regional Legal Products	Article 89 Paragraph (1)	Facilitation carried out by the Minister through the Director General of Regional Autonomy for provinces and the governor for districts/cities is carried out no later than 15 (fifteen) days after receiving the Facilitation request letter.	Facilitation carried out by the Minister through the Director General of Regional Autonomy for provinces and by the governor for districts/cities, must be provided no later than 15 (fifteen) days from the date of receipt of the facilitation request letter. If this time period has passed and there is no response or decision, the facilitation request is deemed to have been facilitated.
Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number I49 of 2024 concerning the Ministry of Home Affairs	Article 19	In carrying out the duties as referred to in Article 18, the Directorate General of Regional Autonomy carries out the following functions: a. formulation of policies in the field of regional administration, special autonomy and special	In carrying out the duties as referred to in Article 18, the Directorate General of Regional Autonomy carries out the following functions: a. formulation of policies in the field of regional planning, special autonomy and special regions, administration of

		<p>regions, administration of regional heads and Regional Representative Councils, general development of regional institutions, personnel in regional apparatus, and regional legal products, as well as evaluation of regional government administration;</p> <p>b. implementation of policies and coordination in the field of regional planning, special autonomy and special regions, administration of regional heads and Regional People's Representative Councils, general development of regional institutions, personnel in regional apparatus, and regional legal products, as well as evaluation of regional government administration;</p>	<p>regional heads and Regional Representative Councils, general development of regional institutions, personnel in regional apparatus, and regional legal products, as well as evaluation of the implementation of regional government;</p> <p>b. implementation of policies and coordination in the field of regional planning, special autonomy and special regions, administration of regional heads and Regional Representative Councils, general development of regional institutions, personnel in regional apparatus, and evaluation of regional government administration and regional legal products which include facilitation, harmonization, consolidation, and strengthening of the concept of drafting regional legal products.</p>
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The consequence of this shift in authority is that all regulations related to the authority of the Ministry of Law in harmonizing, rounding, consolidating and facilitating the conception of draft regional legal products as long as they relate to follow-up of optional authority are not the authority of the Ministry of Law, as in the provisions of the Regulation of the Minister of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2024 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Ministry of Law, Article 96 letter g, Articles 113, 114, Article 165 and other provisions must be interpreted in the context of the scope of implementation of the absolute authority of the Central Government.

The same interpretation also applies to the Circular Letter of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number M.HH-01.PP.04.02 of 2022 concerning Procedures and Procedures for Harmonizing, Rounding, and Consolidating the Concept of Draft Regional Regulations and Draft Regulations of Regional Heads. Through this mechanism, the Ministry of Home Affairs can also provide more transparent and measurable responses to regions regarding perceived or doubtful discrepancies between their policies and central government policies.

The Ministry of Home Affairs will act as a facilitator, providing normative explanations and technical guidance related to the harmonization and creation of regional regulations. This way, local governments will not feel hampered in implementing legal innovations that meet their needs while remaining within the legal framework consistent with the national legal framework.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1) Conclusions

- a. The essence of regional legal products (Perda) is not just legal regulations made by regional governments, but is also a tool to regulate, manage and adjust regional policies according to the needs and characteristics of local communities, within the limits of authority determined by national law;
- b. The current stage of regional legal product development faces a tension between the need for legal certainty and the demand for normative effectiveness. On the one hand, the harmonization procedures carried out by the Ministry of Law and Human Rights emphasize the normative-formal aspect to maintain the compatibility of the national legal system. However, on the other hand, this textual and centralized approach neglects contextual and sociological needs at the regional level, which are essential within the framework of regional autonomy. As a result, the legal certainty established procedurally is often illusory, lacking effective implementation in the field. Legal products that are formally "certain" do not necessarily "function" substantively. A legalistic approach that is not adaptive to local dynamics has the potential to hinder the responsiveness of regional law and create a fragmentation between prevailing norms and the social realities that must be regulated.
- c. The ideal concept for the formation of regional legal products must ensure that each regional regulation is formed based on the principle of real and responsible regional autonomy, in line with the principle of legal certainty and does not conflict with the national legal system. Therefore, it is necessary to implement a limited centralization model in the development of regional legal products based on the principle of subsidiarity, where regions are given the freedom to regulate their affairs with central oversight only on strategic aspects. This model accelerates the acceleration of legal development that is participatory, responsive, and contextual to the needs of regional communities, while maintaining the unity of the national legal system. Harmonization, unification, and strengthening the concept of drafting regional legal products are key to realizing effective, adaptive, and equitable regional legal products within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

2) Suggestions

A paradigm shift is needed in the process of forming regional legislative products, it is no longer sufficient to be interpreted as a process that solely relies on editorial conformity and normative systematics, but must move towards a more contextual, collaborative, and dialogical approach. In order to strengthen the effectiveness of facilitation, harmonization, rounding, and strengthening the concept of drafting regional legal products, a reconstruction of several strategic provisions is carried out. This reconstruction is intended to clarify time limits, emphasize facilitation authority, and expand the scope of fostering regional legal products to align with the principles of effectiveness, legal certainty, and harmony of the national legal system within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

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